

INTEGRITY ASSESSMENT OF CFRP-CONCRETE INTERFACE ON EXTERNALLY STRENGTHENED BRIDGE DIAPHRAGMS USING DIRECT TENSION PULL-OFF TEST

Issa Fowai, University of Ottawa, Canada, ifowa039@uottawa.ca

Martin Noël, University of Ottawa, Canada, martinnoel@uottawa.ca

Beatriz Martín-Pérez, University of Ottawa, Canada, beatriz.martin-perez@uottawa.ca

Leandro Sanchez, University of Ottawa, Canada, leandro.sanchez@uottawa.ca

ABSTRACT

In service, externally bonded CFRP materials may be exposed to fluctuating moisture levels and harsh temperature cycles, which can potentially reduce their durability and degrade the CFRP-concrete bond. This bond interface is the most critical parameter in the structural evaluation of CFRP retrofitted bridges. Full interfacial assessment of the bond behaviour for structural performance evaluation should include the identification of defects, estimation of defect size, the potential effects on structural behaviour, and continuous monitoring of the evolution of the defects over time. In this paper, 490 pull-off tests were conducted following ASTM D7522 to investigate the integrity and variability of the bond strength of the CFRP-concrete interface for an externally strengthened diaphragm from a Canadian bridge having two to four layers of CFRP strips in a bond critical application. The bond strength values, which ranged from 0.66 MPa to 5.54 MPa, generally confirmed the results of non-destructive testing, including acoustic sounding and infrared thermography which aimed to locate hidden defects behind the strengthening layers. Bond strength and failure modes of both defective and defect-free regions are critically analyzed.

KEYWORDS

Bond critical; Direct tension Pull-off; Defects; Diaphragms; Durability

INTRODUCTION

The external bonding of high-strength, lightweight, and corrosion-resistant carbon fibre-reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites to concrete bridges has increased substantially over the last three decades. A great number of these CFRP retrofitting works are undertaken to increase the shear and flexural capacity of deteriorated bridge elements. In these bond-critical applications, the efficiency of the rehabilitation—which depends on the proper transfer of stresses between the CFRP composite material and the concrete substrate—is governed by the behaviour of the CFRP-concrete interface and the properties of the concrete cover (Karbhari & Ghosh, 2009). However, real bridge structures are subjected to a synergistic effect of both loads and environmental influences (freeze-thaw cycles, harsh temperature cycles, moisture intake and humidity) in addition to any initial lapses in installation work that inevitably contribute to the degradation of the CFRP-concrete bond interface over time. Our knowledge about the long-term performance of CFRP retrofits mainly comes from laboratory tests on small-scale samples under controlled conditions. Thus, comprehensive studies on the long-term performance of the CFRP-concrete interface in externally strengthened field structures are needed to ensure a long-lasting solution for aging infrastructure.

Over the years, researchers have conducted various non-destructive tests (NDTs), as well as semi-destructive and destructive testing methods, mainly in laboratory settings, to understand the performance of the bond between composite materials and concrete. The pull-off test is the most popular semi-destructive or destructive evaluation method that can be conducted in both the laboratory and the field to assess the bond strength between the CFRP and the concrete substrate. This test is easy to conduct in-situ and can be easily repeated, making it suitable for quality control and assurance (Fazli et al., 2018). Several variations of pull-off tests exist (ASTMC1583-13, 2013; ASTM D4541, 2017;

ASTMD7522, 2015), all of which are used to measure the tensile capacity of an overlaid material on the concrete substrate. The direct tensile pull-off test version specific to bonded FRP composites is currently standardized in ASTMD7522 (2015).

The pull-off test provides an easily repeatable means of evaluating the bond strength between the CFRP and concrete substrate that has two basic outputs: the tensile bond capacity and failure mode. Failure is expected to occur within the weakest plane of the strengthened system. Since the tensile capacity of the underlying concrete is expected to be much lower than the tensile strength of the structural adhesive at the bond interface, failure in defect-free regions is expected to occur within a few millimetres into the concrete substrate adjacent to the strengthened layer. Seven common modes of failure are defined in (ASTMD7522, 2015) to interpret the potential cause of failure. The failure modes can be adhesive (occurs at the interface), cohesive (occurs within the concrete substrate), or a combination of both (mixed mode). A cohesive failure indicates that the bond that exists between the FRP and the concrete substrate is stronger than the tensile capacity of the concrete.

The pull-off test has been adopted by researchers for several purposes (Banthia et al., 2010; Chen et al., 2014; Fazli et al., 2018; Fowai et al., 2022; Harries & Sweriduk, 2016). In a limited study, (Chen et al., 2014) used the direct tension pull-off test to predict the compressive strength of concrete cubes with design strengths of 30 MPa and 40 MPa. The average relative error observed between the actual cubic compressive strength from a universal testing machine and the estimation from the direct tension pull-off test obtained through regression curves was less than 10 %. Elsewhere, (Harries & Sweriduk, 2016) presented a detailed experimental program on the factors affecting the variability of pull-off test results in concrete substrates. This experimental study included 243 bare concrete specimens (including 147 pre-formed samples during the casting process) subjected to a direct tension pull-off test to investigate variables such as the shape of the cut samples (circular or square), depth of cut, preformed versus hand-drilled specimens, and the effect of pre-torque.

In an accelerated ageing study, (Benzarti et al., 2011) investigated the effect of relative humidity on the bond interface between externally bonded CFRP and concrete substrate. To mimic an in-service ageing environment, samples were first subjected to a temperature of 40°C at a relative humidity of 95% for 628 days. As reported by other authors in the literature (Allen & Atadero, 2012; Banthia et al., 2010; Fazli et al., 2018; Harries & Sweriduk, 2016; Karbhari & Ghosh, 2009; Pallemati et al., 2016), (Benzarti et al., 2011) confirmed the variability of pull-off results even under high quality controlled conditions. They observed a progressive decline in the pull-off strength of the tested concrete slabs and a shift in failure mode from an ideal tensile failure in the concrete to a premature interfacial failure in the adhesive.

In addition to the above laboratory studies, efforts have been made to provide data on the long-term durability of externally bonded CFRP on bridge structures in-service using the direct tension pull-off test (Allen & Atadero, 2012; Banthia et al., 2010), (Pallemati et al., 2016). However, a significant limitation of these studies is the small number of test samples which makes it difficult to confirm the extent of deterioration in the retrofitted work. In addition, in some of these studies, the strength of the underlying concrete that ideally controls failure is not provided, and the mode of failure and number of samples were not specified which makes interpretation of results challenging.

To the authors' knowledge, no previous study has investigated in depth the variability of field-applied CFRP-concrete bond strength after several years in service using a large number of pull-off test results, nor correlated these results with available NDT methods, such as acoustic sounding or infrared thermography and visual inspection. In the condition assessment of multi-layer composite-strengthened elements, determining the actual location of the weak interface after bond degradation between the different layers is still a limitation for NDT. However, conducting a pull-off test after the completion of NDT may provide insight into which interfacial layer between the materials creates a weaker link. Furthermore, the corresponding pull-off bond strength can be an indication of the occurrence of environmental degradation or other damage affecting the overall integrity of the repair.

This study utilizes the direct tension pull-off test to investigate the integrity and variability of the CFRP-concrete interface for an externally strengthened bridge diaphragm from a Canadian bridge. The test aims to characterize the quality and variability of the bond under pure tension and investigate the various failure modes in the substrate and CFRP-concrete interface, the effects of pre-existing defects on the pull-off strength and failure modes, and method of scoring (wet or dry). The test was also conducted on the deteriorated concrete region between the CFRP strips to have a baseline value of the pull-off strength of the concrete. To provide a significant data base, approximately 490 pull-off specimens (twice more than any other study) from one of three bridge diaphragms were tested. Furthermore, the direct tension pull-off test will be used for the first time to validate non-destructive test results.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Overview of the strengthened diaphragms and environmental exposure conditions

The strengthened diaphragm was obtained from a bridge superstructure with a highly integrated structural system comprised of precast post-tensioned concrete girders joined together by cast-in-place infill slabs and diaphragms that were transversely post-tensioned. As a result of significant corrosion-induced deterioration, several portions of the bridge were strengthened with CFRP sheets at various intervals throughout the structure's service life. During service, the structure was exposed to harsh environmental conditions that are detrimental to the short- and long-term durability of the composite strengthening schemes. The annual climate varies from warm-humid summers to several months of freezing winter. Multiple freeze-thaw cycles and excessive use of deicing salt in the winter months are common for structures in this region of Canada.

Most of the CFRP repair works on the bridge were undertaken to improve the shear capacity of girders and diaphragms. Visual inspection of the diaphragms revealed similar types of defects for each diaphragm, although their severity varied. The issues ranged from material compatibility between the underlying concrete and the patch mortar, delamination of both the concrete and bonded composites, discolouration due to corrosion products, construction issues such as random placement of rebars, damage likely caused during transportation (scratches on CFRP strips), and other minor blemishes. Other issues such as installation defects (porosity and voids, resin-rich/poor regions at the concrete-composite interface, uneven surfaces) were visible from the cross-sectional cut made at the diaphragm-girder joint. A detailed account of findings from visual inspection and various NDTs prior to the current direct tension pull-off tests are presented in a companion paper (Fowai et al., 2023).

Figure 1: Schematic of CFRP shear strengthened diaphragm

The shear strengthening configuration on the retrofitted components mainly employed vertical U-wraps in two layers (the sheets are continuous around the member's bottom) with horizontal strips (additional two layers) at the top and bottom providing anchorage (Figure 1).

Composite strengthening work on these three diaphragms was achieved with flexible CFRP sheets through a wet lay-up process. Each diaphragm was strengthened with six double-layer vertical strips

with a width of approximately 305 mm and spaces between each strip ranging from 135 mm to 150 mm. Thickness of the strips (two layers) extracted for coupon testing was estimated between 3.2 mm to 3.5 mm. The thickness of the concrete diaphragm in this study is 220 mm, weighing approximately 4.2 metric tons. A typical post-tensioned diaphragm was reinforced with five internal post-tensioning tendons unevenly distributed along the depth, each comprised of 12 strands with diameters of 7 mm. These tendons were horizontally placed; hence, their contribution to shear capacity was achieved indirectly through axial compression in the concrete.

Material Properties

Based on available information, the expected material properties of the CFRP sheets used to strengthen the bridge are shown in Table 1. Material coupons will be tested at a later date to confirm these properties. The as-is compressive strength of the concrete, obtained from three core samples, is 77.7 MPa.

Table 1 Properties of repair materials (obtained from manufacturer’s product data sheet)

Constituent materials	Young’s modulus (MPa)	Design tensile strength (MPa)	Design thickness (mm)	Elongation (%)
CFRP	94,000	1012	1.3	1.1
Impregnation resins	1724	55	-	3

The epoxy-based bond agent that was used to adhere the loading disc to the specimen surface is a two-component (with a 2:1 by volume mixing ratio), high-strength, and high-modulus epoxy paste. This adhesive has a standard curing time of 72 hours at 21° C.

Preparation of test specimens

A total of 490 pull-off samples were drilled over the entire surface of one side of a diaphragm. Pull-off samples from the CFRP strips were drilled using both wet and dry/hot scoring approaches using the drill shown in Figure 2a. To eliminate sliding of the core drill during the initial drilling process, a wooden plate with a 50 mm diameter hole was used to constrain movement (Figure 2). This wooden plate was removed soon after drilling a few millimetres into the concrete substrate.

Figure 2: Surface drilling process

Surface preparation prior to bonding the loading disc was carried out in the following sequence: the concrete or CFRP surface was abrasively cleaned with medium-grit sandpaper. Compressed air was then used to free the surface of all dust, laitance, and foreign inhibitors that could hinder the bond. Acetone was later applied to clean the surface of any further impurities before the discs were bonded to the specimens. The two-component adhesive was uniformly mixed for approximately five minutes using a drill, and each loading disc was wiped with acetone and allowed to dry prior to applying the adhesive. Finally, the epoxy bond agent was applied to the loading discs using a hand trowel and a heavy-duty mounting tape was applied to keep the specimen in place during curing (Figure 3).

a) Uncleaned discs b) Cleaned: Grinded & Sanded discs c) Curing samples

Figure 3: Work sequence

To regulate the temperature to the manufacturer’s recommended curing temperature, a portable infrared heater was used to slightly heat the concrete prior to and just after bonding. After testing, an angle grinder was used to cut off each failed specimen perfectly (at the CFRP-adhesive interface) of the loading disc for further microscopic and chemical testing of the failure interface. 40-grit and 60-grit sandpapers were then used to clean the disc for subsequent tests, as shown in Figure 3a and b.

Test apparatus and method of testing

The experimental setup consists of a pull-off tester, a loading fixture, and an epoxy adhesive. Figure 4 presents the general steps followed for testing.

Figure 4 General procedures for direct tension pull-off test

The Proceq DY-225 device used in this study directly records the peak load, automatically calculates the bond strength, and allows the user to enter the failure mode directly into the machine (Figure 5). In accordance with (ASTMD7522, 2015), testing was conducted at a loading rate of 1 MPa/min until the dolly (loading fixture) detached with a portion of either material. The pull-off tester was maintained at an orientation perpendicular to the test surface throughout the test as depicted in Figure 4. The load recorded at the time of failure/rupture is known as the maximum bond force. The pull-off bond strength is calculated by simply dividing the peak force by the area of the dolly, as given by Eq. 1:

$$\sigma_p = \frac{4F_p}{\pi D^2} \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

In this expression, σ_p is the pull-off strength or the tensile capacity of the bond, F_p is the peak load obtained at failure, and D represents the diameter of the testing disc (50 mm).

Figure 5 User interface of DY-225

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Failure modes

Several different failure modes were observed during testing. Premature adhesive failure due to debonding of the testing disc at the interface between the loading fixture and the top layer of the CFRP sheet was originally observed for 55 samples (Figure 6). This type of failure is usually rare in pull-off applications and is normally attributed to improper bonding of the loading disc. The relatively high number of failures corresponding to mode A in this test was a result of low winter temperatures and malfunction of the building's heating system, which saw the laboratory temperature drop to less than nine degrees Celsius (in contrast to the 27 degrees recommended by the manufacturer) which prevented adequate curing of the epoxy. This premature debonding was concentrated in CFRP strip 2, concrete strip 2 and CFRP strip 3. However, these samples were all retested with the curing temperature adjusted to the manufacturer's recommendation using external heating lamps. 80 % of the retested mode A samples failed in the substrate (mode G), while the remaining 20 % failed under a mixed mode condition (partial failure in concrete and CFRP).

Figure 6 Premature adhesive failure (ASTM Mode A failure)

Out of the 490 tested samples, 391 were samples extracted from the CFRP strips while the remaining 99 samples were from concrete gaps between the individual strips of CFRP as shown in Figure 2b. The most common failure type among all the 391 pull-off samples from the CFRP strips was the ideal cohesive failure in the concrete substrate (ASTM mode G), accounting for 96.2 % (376 samples) of all CFRP tested samples (Figure 7). This implies a strong bond between the majority of the concrete diaphragm surface and the CFRP composite after several years of exposure to harsh environmental conditions, which also agrees with estimation of defective area observed earlier by NDT (described in a separate paper).

Figure 7 Cohesive concrete failure (ASTM Mode G failure)

Additionally, three samples failed during the original drilling process. These samples were identified as defective (delaminated) areas during the non-destructive testing phase (described in more detail in a separate paper). A complete separation at the interface between the first layer of CFRP and the concrete was witnessed as depicted in Figure 8. Thus, stress transfer between the concrete and the CFRP was compromised at this location.

Figure 8 Debonding of defective regions during drilling with a piece attached to the drilling device

Similarly, a mixed-mode failure was observed for only 12 of the tested CFRP samples (3.1 %). In contrast, none of the tested samples experienced a brooming failure (intralaminar failure), commonly observed in accelerated aging tests in the laboratory (Karbhari & Ghosh, 2009). The distribution of failure modes per CFRP strip is summarized in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Distribution of failure modes per CFRP strip

Pull-off strength results

Another key output of the pull-off test is the determination of the tensile bond strength. This distribution of bond strength over a given strengthened surface gives insight into the degradation of the bond capacity over time, especially when a comparison can be made between the baseline values (obtained at the time the CFRP was first installed). The pull-off values were scattered, with values ranging from 0 MPa (for defective areas previously identified by NDT that failed during the drilling process) to 5.54 MPa for a sound bond. The average bond strength value of the 391 CFRP tested samples was 3.30 MPa with a coefficient of variation of 26.8 %. The mean value for the concrete strips only was 3.42 MPa with a coefficient of variation of 19.4 %. The average bond strength of all 490 samples was 3.32 MPa with a coefficient of variation of 25 %. The range of values and the overall distribution of bond strength

is presented in Figure 10. It is interesting to note that only approximately 5.1 % (20 samples) of all CFRP tested pull-off samples had bond strength values less than the CSA S6:19 minimum recommended values of 1.5 MPa, even after several years of exposure to severe environmental conditions. Three of the 20 samples with strength below the CSA S6:19 minimum recommended values failed during the drilling process, 14 experienced mode G failure, while 3 showed a mixed mode failure. This observation is direct evidence of the relatively good bond between the strengthened bridge diaphragms and CFRP composite materials.

Figure 10 Distribution of pull-off bond strength values

Figure 11 Contour map of bond strength over the surface

The contour plot shown in Figure 11 summarizes the distribution of bond strength per strip over the entire surface with the black strip showing the untested bottom anchorage strip reserved for another structural test. From these bond strength results, the top anchorage strip (which had the majority of the delamination previously detected by NDT) had the lowest mean of 2.78 MPa and the highest proportion of defective areas.

Figure 12 Bond strength as a function of the drilling method

Another key observation is that even though dry/hot drill does introduce thermal stress in both materials, for shallow depth drilling such as those prescribed by international standards (6-12 mm), the pull-off strength is evidently not necessarily a function of the drill method (Figure 12). The mean values of the wet and dry/hot drill approaches were 3.25 MPa and 3.40 MPa, respectively. The coefficient of variation of the two approaches (wet and hot drilling) were 22.7 % and 22.8 %, respectively. However, whenever possible, preference should be given to wet drills to minimize damage to the drilling equipment.

Validation of NDT results and rationale for variation in pull-off strength

Consistent with the findings of the previous studies using NDT, the pull-off samples with identified defects from NDT showed a significant decrease in pull-off strength and prevailing delamination of the CFRP material. Six of the extremely low values obtained in this research came from the anchorage strip at locations with known defects (Figure 13). Interestingly, these defective regions' average bond strength value (1.55 MPa) was still slightly above the code suggested minimum value. The poor bond at these locations is evident in Figure 13 and Figure 14.

The prevailing failure mode in these regions was a mixed-mode delamination of CFRP occurring at different layers of the composite (Figure 13b and Figure 14): a) Failure at the interface between the first layer and the second layer of CFRP sheets, which indicates a deterioration of the adhesive between the two layers of sheet and a discontinuity in stress transfer; and b) mixed mode failure at the interface between the concrete and the first layer of the CFRP sheet was also observed.

Figure 13 a) Pull-off strength of known defect areas on anchorage strip b) typical delamination failure

The failure surface typically includes a cut through unbonded portions of the CFRP sheet. Notably, values as low as 1.13 MPa, 1.17 MPa and 1.23 MPa were obtained during the pull-off test but undetected by the NDT testing.

Figure 14 Pull-off failure surface showing mixed mode failure at different layers of the material

Generally, the variability in pull-off results is attributed to the heterogeneity of the individual materials (concrete and CFRP-composite). However, for deteriorated structures that have undergone extensive repair work, the level of variance in the pull-off values may increase due to the presence of additional anomalies such as the use of different patch materials, unfilled cavities during surface preparation, inconsistencies during construction (misplaced metal strips), and the existence of joints with uneven stress distribution can individually or collectively alter both the failure strength and fracture propagation in the strengthened substrate (Figure 15).

Through combined NDT and semi-destructive pull-off tests, an informed decision can be reached on areas of the composite materials that need additional testing for microanalysis. This can be vital for structures with limited documentation of repair materials.

a) Patch mortar b) Epoxy injection c) Unfilled cavity d) Discontinuity at joint e) Metal strip
 Figure 15 Rationale for additional variability in pull-off tests

Conclusions

This paper used the direct tension pull-off test to evaluate the integrity of the bond between CFRP composite and concrete bridge diaphragm from a major Canadian bridge after several years of exposure to environmental and load-induced degradation. A total of 490 pull-off samples (391 from CFRP strengthened area and 99 samples from concrete gaps between CFRP sheets) were drilled to provide a substantial database. The pull-off test results obtained from this work led to the following conclusions:

- The direct tension pull-off test is a quick and reliable technique to cross-validate NDT results of externally bonded repairs.
- It allows for the determination of both the bond strength and the specific layer in a multi-layer composite application where failure will initiate, with a decrease in bond strength signifying a degradation at that specific location.
- While concrete is the weakest link in sound regions in terms of inherent tensile capacity, different fracture surfaces such as those highlighted in this work should be expected depending on the level of deterioration at the bond-line.
- Based on the pull-off test results from this study, approximately 96 % of the tested CFRP pull-off samples from the deteriorated concrete diaphragm experienced an ideal failure in concrete. This is a testimony of the relatively good bond between CFRP and concrete and extensive exposure to service loads and harsh climate conditions.
- Furthermore, these failure modes can be influenced by inconsistencies in construction and installation processes and the presence of substantial patch cementitious materials.
- The distribution of pull-off strength obtained shows the variability of the pull-off test method. However, it is shown in this work that code prescribed minimum values may be far less than the pull-off strength value even for strengthened members that have experienced degradation in field conditions. Thus, current standards appear to be conservative.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to acknowledge the National Science and Engineering Council of Canada (NSERC) for providing the funding for this research and Simpson Strongtie for their contribution to this research.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest in creating this research paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- Allen, D. G., & Atadero, R. A. (2012). Evaluating the long-term durability of externally bonded FRP via field assessments. *Journal of composites for construction*, 16(6), 737-746.
- ASTMC1583-13. (2013). *Standard Test Method for Tensile Strength of Concrete Surfaces and the Bond Strength Or Tensile Strength of Concrete Repair and Overlay Materials by Direct Tension (pull-off Method)*. ASTM International.
- ASTMD4541. (2017). Standard test method for pull-off strength of coatings using portable adhesion testers. *ASTM International: West Conshohocken, PA, USA*.
- ASTMD7522. (2015). Standard test method for pull-off strength for FRP laminate systems bonded to concrete substrate.
- Banthia, N., Abdolrahimzadeh, A., Demers, M., Mufti, A., & Sheikh, S. (2010). Durability of FRP-concrete bond in FRP-strengthened bridges. *Concrete International*, 32(8), 45-51.
- Benzarti, K., Chataigner, S., Quiertant, M., Marty, C., & Aubagnac, C. (2011). Accelerated ageing behaviour of the adhesive bond between concrete specimens and CFRP overlays. *Construction and Building Materials*, 25(2), 523-538.
- Chen, C., Jin, W., Ding, H., Zhao, Y., Muhammed Basheer, P., & Magee, B. J. (2014). Experimental research on concrete strength prediction by Limpet pull-off test in China. *International Journal of Structural Engineering* 3, 5(1), 1-12.
- Fazli, H., Yassin, A. M., Shafiq, N., & Teo, W. (2018). Pull-off testing as an interfacial bond strength assessment of CFRP-concrete interface exposed to a marine environment. *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 84, 335-342.
- Fowai, I., Noël, M., Martin-Perez, B., & Sanchez, L. (2022). Evaluation of interfacial debonding of fibre-reinforced polymer using variable angle peel test. In *Bridge Safety, Maintenance, Management, Life-Cycle, Resilience and Sustainability* (pp. 2526-2532). CRC Press.
- Fowai, I., Noël, M., Martin-Perez, B., & Sanchez, L. (2023). *Integrity assessment of CFRP-concrete interface on externally strengthened bridge diaphragms using direct tension pull-off test* 11th International Conference on FRP composites in civil engineering, Rio de Janeiro.
- Harries, K., & Sweriduk, M. (2016). Factors affecting direct tension pull-off test results of materials bonded to concrete. *Advances in Civil Engineering Materials*, 5(1), 353-370.
- Karbhari, V. M., & Ghosh, K. (2009). Comparative durability evaluation of ambient temperature cured externally bonded CFRP and GFRP composite systems for repair of bridges. *Composites part A: Applied science and manufacturing*, 40(9), 1353-1363.
- Pallempati, H., Beneberu, E., & Yazdani, N. (2016). Evaluation of external FRP-concrete bond in repaired concrete bridge girders and columns. *Innovative Infrastructure Solutions*, 1(1), 1-8.